

Increase of IL-17 expression on Th2 cells in asthma by cytokine-induced microenvironment

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SUPPLEMENTARY METHODS

Mice. Female C57BL/6 WT mice (6-8 weeks old) were obtained from the breeding facility of Ribeirao Preto Medical School, University of Sao Paulo (Brazil). Animals were maintained in specific-pathogen-free conditions by microisolator cages (Alesco, Brazil) receiving food and water ad libitum. All experiments were performed according to the local Ethics Committee on Animal Experimentation (Protocol Number 116/2018).

OVA-induced asthma model. Mice were sensitized weekly three times in seven-day intervals with OVA grade VI (10 µg) plus aluminum hydroxide (alum, 2 mg) (Sigma) by intraperitoneal route (200 µL / animal). Seven days after the last sensitization, mice were challenged three consecutive days with OVA grade V (30 µg) (Sigma) by intranasal route. Animals were euthanized 24 hours after the last OVA challenge, by intraperitoneal inoculation of anesthetic solution containing 20% ketamine hydrochloride (Agener, Brazil) and 10% xilasin (Laboratorios Calier SA, Spain).

Culture and infection with *S. pneumoniae*. TIGR4 strain of *S. pneumoniae* (ATCC BAA-334) frozen at -80°C in tryptone soy broth (TSB) (BD, cat. 211825) containing 10% glycerol was thawed, plated on blood agar and incubated overnight at 37°C, 5% CO₂. After growth, colonies were inoculated in TSB (OD600 = 0.06) and incubating for 4 to 5 hours (OD600 = 0.3). Bacterial suspension was plated on blood agar and incubated overnight. Growth bacteria was adjusted to 50 x 10⁸ / mL of colony-forming unit (CFU) in sterile Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS). Mice were infected with 1 x 10⁸ CFU of *S. pneumoniae* by intranasal route (20 µL / animal) during the second challenge with OVA. Animals were euthanized 48 hours after the infection.

Bronchoalveolar lavage. Bronchoalveolar lavage fluids (BALF) were obtained by trachea cannulation with subsequent three washes with iced PBS. Samples were collected, centrifuged and supernatants were stored at -20°C for cytokine measurement. Red cells were removed by Ammonium-Chloride-Potassium (ACK) buffer and cell suspensions were centrifuged in cytocentrifuge (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The cells were stained with rapid panoptic (Labor Clin, Brazil) for differential cell count, as previously described (Martins et al., 2021).

Lung cells isolation and culture. After euthanasia, lungs were perfused with 5 mL of PBS through the right ventricle. Perfused lung lower right lobes were cut into small pieces and digested for 50 min at 37°C, 5% CO₂ with collagenase type IV (2.2 mg/mL) (Sigma) and DNase (0.055 mg/mL) (Roche). The digestion stopped using EDTA (10 mM). Cell suspensions were passed through a cell strainer, centrifuged, lysed with ACK buffer, and resuspended in complete RPMI 1640 (Sigma), as previously described (Martins et al., 2021).

Patients. Blood samples were collected from 8 patients enrolled at the Hospital das Clinicas (Ribeirao Preto Medical School, University of Sao Paulo, Ribeirao Preto, Brazil), from September 2023 to March 2024, after written informed consent from patients or their surrogates (Certificate of Presentation of Ethical Appreciation 67810623.8.0000.5440). Eligibility criteria included age \geq 18 years with a confirmed asthma diagnostic. Exclusion criteria included patients with DPOC and the occurrence of respiratory infections or use of systemic corticosteroids in the last 6 months before sample collection. All research subjects received pertinent information about this study and signed the informed consent form to participate in this research. Demographic and clinical findings data were collected from the electronic medical records, as presented in **Table S1**.

Th2 and Th17 human cells. Blood samples were collected with EDTA and mononuclear cells were isolated using Ficoll gradient. CD4⁺ cells were isolated using magnetic column (Miltenyi Biotec) and cultured overnight with anti-CD3 (1 μ g/mL) and anti-CD28 (1 μ g/mL) mAb (BD Biosciences) and recombinant IL-2 (10 U/mL, PeproTech) to stimulate IL-4 secretion. Sorting of Th2 (IL-4⁺ cells) cells was performed labelling CD4⁺ cells with fluorescence dye-labelled anti-IL-4 mAb (cytokine secretion assay – detection kit, Miltenyi Biotec) in FACS Aria (BD Biosciences). Sorted Th2 cells were cultured (0.5 x 10⁶ cells / mL) with plate-bound anti-CD3 mAb (1 μ g/mL; OKT3) and soluble anti-CD28 (1 μ g/mL; 28.2) (BD Biosciences) for 5 days in the presence of recombinant cytokines IL-1 β (10 ng/mL), IL-21 (100 ng/mL) and IL-23 (50 ng/mL) (PeproTech), in addition to anti-IFN- γ and anti-IL-4 mAb (10 μ g/mL) (BD Bioscience).

Flow cytometry. Isolated lung cells were adjusted to 1 x 10⁶ cells / sample and cultured with PMA (50 ng/mL, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA), ionomycin (500 ng/mL, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) and monensin / brefeldin A (BD Biosciences, San Jose, CA, USA) for 4 hours. Then, cells were stained with FVS780 viability dye (BD Pharmingen) for

15 minutes at room temperature, and extracellular staining (CD45, CD3 and CD4) was performed according to manufacturer's instructions (BD Pharmingen). For GATA3, ROR γ t and IL-17 staining, cells were permeabilized and fixed before intranuclear/intracellular staining. Th2 human cells were stained with CD4 and IL-17 after culture with Th17 cell differentiation cocktail. Samples were fixed with paraformaldehyde 1% (Labsynth, Diadema, Brazil) and acquired in FACS Canto or in FACS Melody (BD Biosciences). One or two hundred thousand events per sample were collected and analyzed according to size, granularity and fluorescence intensity in singlets and viable cells (FVS-) using FlowJo X 10.0.7r2 software for Windows (Becton Dickinson and Company).

Statistical Analysis. The raw data were initially analyzed for normal distribution (Kolmogorov–Smirnov test) and, considering parametric data, to compare two groups, Student's T-test was applied and to compare three or more groups one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's multiple comparison test was applied. Statistical analyzes and graphs were performed using GraphPad PrismVersion 8 (GraphPad Software for Windows, Inc., San Diego, CA, USA). Values of $p < 0.05$ were considered significant and exact p value was showed in each graph and individual values was presented.

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE

Table S1. Demographic and clinical findings of asthmatic patients.

Asthmatic (n = 8)	Data (mean ± SD)
Age (year)	41.86 ± 12.75
Female, n (%)	75
BMI (kg/m ²)	23.03 ± 2.64
FVC (L)	3.33 ± 0.80
(%)	97.2 ± 3.96
FEV1 (L)	2.19 ± .69
(%)	77 ± 15.89
FEV1/FVC	0.65 ± 0.13
Red blood cells (10 ⁶ /μL)	4.59 ± 0.23
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	13.67 ± 0.83
Leukocytes (10 ³ /μL)	5.71 ± 1.56
Basophils (10 ³ /μL)	0.00
(%)	0.50 ± 0.32
Eosinophils (10 ³ /μL)	0.32 ± 0.17
(%)	5.62 ± 3.13
Neutrophils (10 ³ /μL)	3.11 ± 1.13
(%)	53.7 ± 7.03
Lymphocytes (10 ³ /μL)	1.88 ± 0.54
(%)	34.30 ± 5.73
Monocytes (10 ³ /μL)	0.33 ± 0.05
(%)	5.83 ± 1.85
Platelets (10 ³ /μL)	253.83 ± 43.69
Total IgE (kU/L)	245.88 ± 238.58

BMI: body mass index; FVC: forced vital capacity; FEV1: forced expiratory volume; FEV1/FVC: forced vital capacity / forced expiratory volume ratio; IgE: immunoglobulin E.